

INCREASING ACCESSIBILITY OF AUDIOVISUAL CONTENT USING WHISPER

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Abstract - Captions are essential to the searchability, discoverability, and accessibility of audiovisual (AV) materials. However, creating captions is often challenging due to the resources required. With data collected from a grant-funded project, this poster describes the impact of Whisper [1], an open-source automated speech recognition (ASR) software, on captioning work at Emory Libraries, observing that Whisper increased capacity for captioning without entailing a reduction in staff time, due to increasing demand and the ongoing need for human review in providing accurate, high-quality captions. The project methodology and findings will be presented along with implications for digital preservation and leveraging ASR-generated captions in metadata enhancement.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Many organizations face the challenge of ensuring that AV content is accessible to all audiences. Captioning AV content improves searchability, discoverability, and accessibility for end users. However, creating captions through traditional in-house or outsourced transcription is often extremely resource intensive.

In 2023, Emory Libraries was awarded a Lyrasis Catalyst Fund grant to assess the viability of Whisper, an open-source AI software, as a solution to captioning and transcribing AV content, and to develop resources that could be used to caption and transcribe digital audiovisual materials at large scale.

Over the course of the grant, we processed 250 hours of AV content through Whisper, and the resulting caption and transcript files were corrected by a team of student editors. Data was collected on optimal hardware and software configurations, processing times, power consumption, average editing times, and word error rates. We also created editing style guides and documented the project's caption creation and editing workflows. This poster will describe the methodologies and findings of the project, and their implications for using Whisper and ASR tools in increasing AV content accessibility.

II. METHOD

To provide data for PC and Mac environments, we processed the content using Whisper on a PC and Whisper.cpp, an open-source port of Whisper to C++, on a Mac. We collected power usage data through HWiNFO on the PC and iStat Menus on the Mac.

We created a project style guide to advise our student editors on how to transcribe speech and describe non-speech audio content. Our guide draws from the Described and Captioned Media Program Captioning Key [2]. It also provides controlled vocabulary resources and cultural and historical context for the collections. The students used CADET [3] to edit the captions and transcripts.

We assessed accuracy using the word error rate (WER) metric, first normalizing files for capitalization, punctuation, and spacing, and then comparing the Whisper and Whisper.cpp outputs with the versions corrected by student editors.

III. FINDINGS

Whisper and Whisper.cpp ran with similar speed, averaging 18.5 and 15.8 minutes per hour of content, respectively. The average power usage was 60W per content hour for the PC and 11W per content hour for the Mac, which is comparable to other digital preservation activities in our department.

Whisper performed most accurately with content featuring minimal music, singing, background noise, or crosstalk; average WER ranged from 5% for collections with optimal characteristics to 24% for collections with extensive crosstalk, singing, and music. Although WER does not measure the impact of word errors on semantic meaning, it illuminated strengths and weaknesses, and its results aligned with observational data from our editors.

Finally, editing time averaged 4.6 hours per hour of content, with variation across collections ranging from 3.3 to 10.7 hours per content hour. Accuracy played a significant role in the amount of editing time required, as did media format; audio transcripts were faster to edit than video captions.

The poster will describe these findings and provide links to the resources created through the project: hardware and software configurations, style guide examples, benchmark statistics, and project workflows. These resources can be used and adapted by institutions engaged in captioning work regardless of how the captions are initially created.

IV. OUTLOOK

Based on the data gathered, Whisper can be a viable tool for captioning and transcription of AV material due to its cost, accuracy, and ease of running locally for data privacy. However, human involvement is essential; firstly to identify and correct plausible-sounding but made-up text that sometimes occurs in the output, but more broadly, we found that greater availability of captions led to increased expectations for caption availability and increased demand for captioning work. Rather than replacing human roles, implementing Whisper resulted in new jobs to meet this increased demand. Whisper also had a transformative impact for our editors. Because it performed the most labor-intensive task of creating the initial text, Whisper increased editors' work satisfaction, as they were able to focus on making editorial choices, which they found more intellectually engaging.

V. CONCLUSION

As AI transcription becomes more widespread and standards like the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines [4] become more widely adopted, user expectations for caption availability are likely to increase. Whisper expands our capacity to meet this demand and favorably transforms the experience of captioning staff. The poster will discuss these findings as well as new opportunities for enhancing AV discoverability through the use of caption and transcript files in text searches and metadata creation or enhancement. Access is fundamental to preservation; a Whisper-facilitated captioning program supports digital preservation by ensuring that digital collections are available, useable, and understandable to users of all abilities.

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